

Identifying Problems and Suggestions for Improving the Services N-LIST E-Resources for Better Academic Pursuits

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Abstract

This research paper explains the usage of the N-LIST e-resources among the students and faculty members of the various select degree colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method was used as a tool for collection of data from the 32 select degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The total data was collected from 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are user (faculty and student) respondents and 180 are non-user (faculty and student) respondents. The statistical test has been applied and the inferences have been drawn thereof for identifying the problems of N-LIST e-resources and to provide suggestions for aiming at improving the users' academic pursuits and learning outcomes.

Keywords: E-books, E-journals, Bibliographical databases, N-LIST, INFLIBNET, Academic pursuits, Learning outcomes, Degree colleges of Panjab University

Introduction

With the advent of resource sharing, the library consortia have brought economy, efficiency and equality in information availability and its usage. Through library consortia, the gap between information resource-rich libraries and resource-deficient libraries is expected to be bridged. Although there are many consortia in India like UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortia, INDEST Consortia, CSIR Consortia, etc., which have already gained popularity in India, yet N-LIST is one such consortia which helps to bridge this gap and provides access to e-resources to its users.

N-LIST: An Initiative of NMEICT

The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) was launched on 3rd

Feb, 2009. It initiated a project called "National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)", popularly known as N-LIST which was formally launched by Shri Kapil Sibal, Union Minister for Human Resource Development, on 4th May, 2010.¹ The N-LIST Project is being jointly executed by the (University Grants Commission- Information Network) UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi. The project provides cross-subscription to e-resources subscribed by the two consortia, i.e., subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and UGC-INFONET resources for technical institutions; and the access to selected e-resources to colleges.

The faculty and the students from the colleges covered under section 12B/2F of the UGC Act are eligible to access

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e-resources through the N-LIST project. These colleges are required to register themselves on the N-LIST website. During the last three years, the collection has increased from 2100 to 6000 e-journals and from 51,000 to 100,000 e-books, subscribed under the N-LIST Project.²

Review of Literature

Akinola¹ obtained the results from her study which revealed that majority of the respondents (35.4%) from the University of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for preparing class lectures. The study on information-seeking behavior of Social Science Faculty was done by Chattwal³ which indicates the pen-drive is most preferred as an external storage device due to its large storage capacity as well as convenience of usage was found to be the most preferred by 50.20% participants. The database appears to be the most suitable usage pattern for the university faculty members. The present study indicates that the main reason for not using N-LIST e-resources is 'lack of awareness' by student non-user respondents. A similar study by Nikam and Pramodini⁶ indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the faculty members and research scholars were: 59.50% of respondents attributed the reason as lack of training/orientation; the other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed it to 'lack of awareness' whereas 10.50% opted 'aware but internet connection is not proper'. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus need constant guidance and training to maximize the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources. A similar study by Bhardwaj and Walia² analyzed the rating of quality of the electronic resources in the St. Stephens College library, where majority of the respondents (52.8%) agreed that the 'quality of the N-LIST e-resources is excellent' while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources as good. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources as very good. A similar study by Chikkanmanju and Kumbar⁹ identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST e-resources of the Tumkur University. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST e-resources.

Objectives of the Study

The present study is an attempt to find out the accessibility of N-LIST e-resources and the usage trends used by the faculty and students of the Panjab University, Chandigarh.

The study was conducted with the following objectives:

- To identify the problems encountered by the faculty and student users, while seeking information.
- To analyze the suggestions provided by the faculty and students users for improving the services of the N-LIST e-resources.

Methodology and Scope of the Study

A survey method has been implemented to meet the objectives of the study. The author has collected the data through questionnaire method from the select degree colleges, which are affiliated to Panjab University. The data have been collected from the 144 faculty users and 142 student users. In 144 faculty users, 114 are males and 30 are females whereas 142 student users, 33 are males and 109 are females. This method facilitates yearly accumulation of information from the member colleges in various settings under parameters relevant to the study.

Scope and Locale of the Study

This study is confined to 32 member colleges. These member colleges are located in Punjab and Chandigarh and are affiliated to Panjab University only.

Time Period of the Study

The time period of the study was from Jan 2010 to May 2015.

Demography

Demography refers to the fundamental and measurable statistics of a population with characteristics such as gender, age, education, etc., to which the faculty and student users belong to. Table 1 provides demographic statistics of student user respondents in terms of gender, age, and education. The analysis of the data has been done in the following manner:

Table 1. Demography of Faculty and Student (User)

Faculty (User)			Student (User)		
		N (%)			N (%)
Gender N=144	Male	30 (20.83%)	Gender N=142	Male	33 (23.24%)
	Female	114 (79.17%)		Female	109 (76.76%)
Age N=144	25–34	84 (58.33%)	Age N=142	18-21	80 (56.34%)
	35–44	60 (41.67%)		22–24	58 (40.85%)
	Above 44	0 (0%)		Above 24	4 (2.82%)
Designation N=144	Professor	3 (2.08%)	Education N=142	Pursuing Graduate	23 (16.20%)
	Associate Professor	17 (11.81%)		Pursuing Postgraduate	119 (83.80%)
	Assistant Professor	124 (86.11%)			

Gender

The gender-wise distribution of respondents is presented in Fig. 1. The responses have been received from male and female respondents from the colleges through a detailed investigation. It has been analyzed that out of 144 faculty users, 79.17% respondents are females while 20.83% are males whereas in the student users there are total 142 respondents from which 76.76% are the females and 23.24% are males. The above data reveals that the representation of female respondents is much more than that of the male respondents in both the categories.

Analysis

(A) Problems Encountered by the Respondents while Using N-LIST E-resources

In order to understand the usage of N-LIST e-Resources, it is necessary to know the pros and cons of the same. So, the researchers tried to identify the various hindrances/problems which the users faced while obtaining information.

Table 2. Problems Encountered by the Faculty Respondents while Seeking Information

S. No.	Factors/Problems	Always	Frequently	Sometimes	Seldom	Never	Total
		N (%)					
1	Lack of technical know-how	22 15.28%	34 23.61%	52 36.11%	36 25.00%	0 0.00%	144 (100.00%)
2	Lack of Awareness regarding database literacy	23 15.97%	29 20.14%	51 35.42%	33 22.92%	8 5.56%	144 (100.00%)
3	Provides the Irrelevant Information	0 0.00%	21 14.58%	59 40.97%	40 27.78%	24 16.67%	144 (100.00%)
4	Difficult in Framing search strategy	33 22.92%	18 12.50%	41 28.47%	49 34.03%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)
5	Irrelevant Article in spite of Journals subscriptions	13 9.03%	32 22.22%	55 38.19%	8 5.56%	36 25.00%	144 (100.00%)
6	Adverse Effect on Health	13 9.03%	19 13.19%	49 34.03%	18 12.50%	45 31.25%	144 (100.00%)
7	Language Barrier	0 0.00%	12 8.33%	64 44.44%	19 13.19%	49 34.03%	144 (100.00%)
8	Lack of Library Support	8 5.56%	25 17.36%	53 36.81%	11 7.64%	47 32.64%	144 (100.00%)
9	No Update Information	14 9.72%	28 19.44%	57 39.58%	14 9.72%	31 21.53%	144 (100.00%)
10	Searching Journal Contents	5 3.47%	19 13.19%	66 45.83%	14 9.72%	40 27.78%	144 (100.00%)
11	Subject related Queries	10 6.94%	42 29.17%	51 35.42%	7 4.86%	34 23.61%	144 (100.00%)
12	No back Files	14 9.72%	18 12.50%	67 46.53%	7 4.86%	38 26.39%	144 (100.00%)
13	Curriculum Based Queries have not been solved	14 9.72%	30 20.83%	57 39.58%	35 24.31%	8 5.56%	144 (100.00%)
14	Unsolved Research Problems	22 15.28%	53 36.81%	26 18.06%	37 25.69%	6 4.17%	144 (100.00%)
15	Malware Problem	32 22.22%	6 4.17%	57 39.58%	41 28.47%	8 5.56%	144 (100.00%)

From combining the scores of ‘Always’ (A) and ‘Frequently’ (F), it was comprehended that majority of faculty respondents, i.e., 52.09% (A=15.28%+F=36.81%) considered ‘Unsolved Research Problems’ followed by ‘lack of technical know-how’ opted by 38.89% (A=15.28%+F=23.61%) of faculty respondents, which is a major barrier in seeking information. Another most often encountered problem was ‘lack of awareness regarding database literacy’ by 36.11% (A=15.97%+F=20.14%) of faculty respondents. While 35.42% (A=22.92%+F=12.50%) of respondents faced ‘difficulty in framing the search strategy’ which problem the faculty often faced while seeking information.

From the scores of the ‘sometimes’, it was observed that the majority of faculty respondents, i.e., 46.53% considered ‘no back files’ as a problem followed by 44.44% of participants who feel ‘language barrier’ as one of the hindrances in using

of N-LIST e-resources. The 45.83% of faculty respondents find difficulty in searching the TOC, which is also one of the barriers in the usage of N-LIST e-resources. 40.97% express that it provides irrelevant information while 39.58% and 38.19% state that there is ‘lack of updated information; unsolved curriculum based queries’ and ‘irrelevant articles in spite of journal subscription’ which is also considered as one of the problems encountered by the faculty users. Whereas 34.03% of faculty respondents feel that the e-resources affect their health as the continuous work on laptop/PC may cause adverse effect on the eyes and back. But 35.42% of faculty respondents considered ‘unsolved subject related queries’ as a mild factor while using N-LIST e-resources.

From the scores of ‘never’, it was evinced that 34.03% of faculty respondents do not face any language barrier

followed by 32.64% of faculty users feel no obstacle in library support as they are fully satisfied with the same, while 34.03% rarely faced problem in 'framing the search strategy'. It has been evinced that none of the faculty members have quoted the lack of technical know-how as a problem.

Thus, it can be comprehended that the majority of

faculty respondents, i.e., 52.09% (A=15.28%+F=36.81%) considered 'unsolved research based problems' followed by 'lack of technical know-how' opted by 38.89% (A=15.28%+F=23.61%) of respondents, which is a major barrier in seeking information.

(B) Problems Encountered by the Student Respondents while Seeking Information

Table 3. Problems Encountered by Student Respondents while Seeking Information

S. No.	Factors/Problems	Always	Frequently	Sometimes	Seldom	Never	Total
		N (%)					
1	Lack of technical know-how	43 30.28%	32 22.54%	46 32.39%	21 14.79%	0 0.00%	142 (100.00%)
2	Lack of awareness regarding database literacy	42 29.58%	45 31.69%	26 18.31%	23 16.20%	6 4.23%	142 (100.00%)
3	Provides irrelevant information	0 0.00%	18 12.68%	86 60.56%	25 17.61%	13 9.15%	142 (100.00%)
4	Difficult in framing the search strategy	37 26.06%	10 7.04%	54 38.03%	37 26.06%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)
5	Irrelevant article in spite of journal subscription	38 26.76%	35 24.65%	32 22.54%	10 7.04%	27 19.01%	142 (100.00%)
6	Adverse effect on health	6 4.23%	32 22.54%	52 36.62%	22 15.49%	30 21.13%	142 (100.00%)
7	Language barrier	0 0.00%	6 4.23%	72 50.70%	26 18.31%	38 26.76%	142 (100.00%)
8	Lack of library support	18 12.68%	13 9.15%	62 43.66%	18 12.68%	31 21.83%	142 (100.00%)
9	No update information	18 12.68%	47 33.10%	36 25.35%	20 14.08%	21 14.79%	142 (100.00%)
10	Searching journal contents	20 14.08%	15 10.56%	90 63.38%	6 4.23%	11 7.75%	142 (100.00%)
11	Unsolved subject-related queries	2 1.41%	65 45.77%	42 29.58%	8 5.63%	25 17.61%	142 (100.00%)
12	No back files	11 7.75%	20 14.08%	64 45.07%	20 14.08%	27 19.01%	142 (100.00%)
13	Unsolved curriculum-based queries	11 7.75%	34 23.94%	64 45.07%	20 14.08%	27 19.01%	142 (100.00%)
14	Malware problem	39 27.46%	24 16.90%	50 35.21%	11 7.75%	18 12.68%	142 (100.00%)

From combining the scores of 'Always' (A) and 'Frequently' (F), it was discussed that majority of student respondents, i.e., 61.27% (A=29.58%+F=31.69%) considered 'lack of awareness regarding database literacy' followed by 'lack of technical know-how' opted by 52.82% (A=30.23%+F=22.54%) of respondents, which is a major barrier in seeking information. Another most often encountered problem was 'irrelevant article in spite of article subscription' by 51.41% (A=26.76%+F=24.65%) of student respondents. While 47.18% (A=1.41%+F=45.77%) and 44.36% (A=27.46%+F=16.90%) of respondents faced problems in 'unsolved subject related queries' and from 'malware problems', which the students considered a hindrance in seeking information.

Considering the scores under 'sometimes', it was understood that 63.38% of student respondents find difficulty in

searching the journal contents followed by 60.56% who feel that it provides irrelevant information. 50.70% of participants encountered in 'language barrier'. 45.07% feel that there are 'no back files' and 'unsolved curriculum based queries' as one of the hindrances in seeking information. 43.66% and 29.58% of student respondents feel that 'lack of library support' and 'unsolved subject related queries' is one of the problems faced by the student users. While 36.62% and 29.58% feel that it affects the health and the subject related queries have been unsolved, this is one of the hindrances in using the N-LIST e-resources, whereas 18.31% of the users considered 'lack of awareness' as a hindrance while using N-LIST e-resources.

From the scores of the 'never' and 'seldom', it was perceived that 26.76% of student respondents never faced any problem in understanding 'language' while using the N-LIST

e-resources followed by 21.83% of student users feeling no issue in library support as they are fully satisfied with the same. 19.01% of participants do not consider any hindrance of multiple database accessibility, unsolved curriculum based queries and no back files while using the N-LIST e-resources, while 26.06% rarely faced any problem in 'framing the search strategy'.

It was thus inferred that majority of student respondents consider 61.27% (A=29.58%+F=31.69%) considered 'lack of awareness regarding database literacy' followed by 'lack of technical know-how' opted by 52.82% (A=30.23%+F=22.54%) of respondents, as the major hindrance while seeking information.

(C) Evaluative Analysis of Problems Faced by Faculty and Student Users

From the above tables, it has been assessed that the students considered 'lack of awareness' as a major

hindrance/problem faced by them while using N-LIST e-resources whereas the faculty feels that their 'research problems' remained unsolved. Whereas both the faculty and student respondents encountered in 'lack of technical know-how' as the second major hindrance while using the N-LIST e-resources. Although both the students and faculty respondents are satisfied with the library support, both find 'difficulty in framing the search strategy'. Thus, it is evident that the users need formal training programs related to search strategy conducted by the libraries.

Suggestions for Improving the Usage of N-LIST E-resources

After filling up the questionnaires, the users were given the option to fill various suggestions in order to eradicate the hindrances/problems while searching the N-LIST e-resources. The suggestions are as follows:

(A) Suggestions for Improving the N-LIST E-resources by Faculty

Table 4. Faculty Suggestions

S. No.	Required/Suggestions	Extremely Required	Moderately Required	Required	Somewhat Required	Not Required	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1	Better searching facilities	29 20.14%	17 11.81%	57 39.58%	41 28.47%	0 0.00%	144 (100.00%)
2	More discipline oriented e-journal	44 30.56%	26 18.06%	33 22.92%	41 28.47%	0 0.00%	144 (100.00%)
3	More discipline-oriented e-Books	45 31.25%	12 8.33%	54 37.50%	30 20.83%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)
4	Single search facility for multiple database	11 7.64%	14 9.72%	70 48.61%	42 29.17%	7 4.86%	144 (100.00%)
5	Training programs	34 23.61%	29 20.14%	31 21.53%	47 32.64%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)
6	Curriculum based e-resource	28 19.44%	20 13.89%	44 30.56%	45 31.25%	7 4.86%	144 (100.00%)
7	Personal assistance	18 12.50%	19 13.19%	75 52.08%	29 20.14%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)
8	Hands on training	29 20.14%	22 15.28%	58 40.28%	32 22.22%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)
9	Place utility	25 17.36%	25 17.36%	52 36.11%	39 27.08%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)
10	Article delivery	30 20.83%	16 11.11%	53 36.81%	42 29.17%	3 2.08%	144 (100.00%)

Table 4 shows the suggestions of the faculty respondents for improving the N-LIST e-resources

From combining the scores of 'extremely required' (ER), 'moderately required' (MR) and 'required' (R), it was analyzed that the majority of the faculty respondents, i.e., 77.08% (ER=31.25%+MR=8.33%+R=37.50%) feel that more discipline-oriented e-books should be added for browsing N-LIST e-resources, while 75.70% (ER=20.14%+MR=15.28%+R=40.28%) of faculty respondents need practical hands on training for understanding the search skills and various sorting

strategies to find the relevant documents and 71.53% (ER=20.14%+MR=11.81%+R=39.58%) considered that the N-LIST should include better searching facilities for browsing the e-resources. Also 68.75% (ER=20.83%+MR=11.11%+R=36.81%) feel that article delivery services are required by the INFLIBNET center. Whereas 65.97% (ER=7.64%+MR=9.72%+R=48.61%) think that there should be a single search facility for multiple database, 65.28% (ER=23.61%+MR=20.14%+R=21.53%) considered that there should be training programs on search skills for the faculty respondents as relevant suggestion for improving the usage of N-LIST e-resources.

From the scores of 'not required' and 'somewhat required', it was perceived that 4.86% of respondents do not require curriculum-based e-resources and single search facility for multiple databases. Only 32.64% of respondents considered training programs as somewhat required suggestions for improving the usage of N-LIST.

It was analyzed that a majority of faculty respondents, i.e., 77.08% feel that more discipline-oriented e-books should be added, which is considered as the most relevant suggestion, followed by 75.70% of faculty respondents considering

'practical hands on training' as an extremely relevant suggestion for improving access to N-LIST e-resources. Hence, It is inferred that the 'addition of more discipline-oriented e-books' and 'practical hands on training' are considered as the most relevant and apt suggestions by the faculty respondents for improving the 'usage of N-LIST e-resources'.

(B) Suggestions for Improving the N-LIST E-resources by Students

Table 5. Student Suggestions

S. No.	Relevant/ Suggestions	Extremely Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Relevant	Somewhat Relevant	Not Relevant	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1	Better searching facilities	39 27.46%	48 33.80%	44 30.99%	11 7.75%	0 0.00%	142 (100.00%)
2	More discipline-oriented e-journal	58 40.85%	34 23.94%	39 27.46%	11 7.75%	0 0.00%	142 (100.00%)
3	More discipline-oriented e-books	53 37.32%	28 19.72%	48 33.80%	9 6.34%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)
4	Single Multiple search facility for database	22 15.49%	25 17.61%	68 47.98%	7 4.93%	20 14.08%	142 (100.00%)
5	Training programs	44 30.99%	29 20.42%	36 25.35%	29 20.42%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)
6	Curriculum-based e-resource	34 23.94%	29 20.42%	46 32.39%	13 9.15%	20 14.08%	142 (100.00%)
7	Personal assistance on special features	36 25.35%	35 24.65%	58 40.85%	9 6.34%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)
8	Hands-on training	37 26.06%	45 31.69%	39 27.46%	17 11.97%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)
9	Place utility	33 23.24%	47 33.10%	47 33.10%	11 7.75%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)
10	Article delivery services	41 28.87%	29 20.42%	49 34.51%	19 13.38%	4 2.82%	142 (100.00%)

Table 5 shows the suggestions of the student respondents for improving the N-LIST e-resources.

From combining the scores of 'extremely required' (ER), 'moderately required' (MR) and 'required' (R), it was deduced that the majority of the student respondents feels that 92.25% (ER=40.85%+R=27.46%) and 90.84% (ER=37.32%+MR=19.72%+R=33.80%) feels that more discipline-oriented e-journals and e-books should be added for browsing N-LIST e-resources. 90.85% (ER=25.35%+MR=24.65%+R=40.85%) of respondents feel that they require 'personal assistance on special features', while 83.80% (ER=28.87%+MR=20.42%+R=34.51%) feel that 'article delivery services' are required by the INFLIBNET center. Whereas 81.01% (ER=15.49%+MR=17.61%+R=47.98%) feel that there should be a single search facility for multiple database, 76.76% (ER=30.99%+MR=20.42%+R=25.35%) considered that there should be training programs on

search skills for the student respondents as relevant suggestion for improving the usage of N-LIST e-resources.

From the scores of 'not required' and 'somewhat required', it was brought to notice that 14.08% considered curriculum-based e-resources should not be added as required suggestion, while 13.38% of respondents think article delivery service as somewhat required suggestion for improving the usage of N-LIST e-resources.

But according to the majority of student respondents, 92.25% and 90.84% preferred more discipline-oriented e-journals and e-books to be added for better browsing, followed by 90.85% participants who considered their urge for training on special features as a relevant suggestion for improving the usage of N-LIST e-resources. Thus it was inferred that 'more discipline-oriented e-journals' and 'personal assistance on special features' is considered the most relevant suggestions by the student respondents for improving the 'usage of N-LIST e-resources'.

(C) Evaluative Analysis of Suggestions for Improving the N-LIST E-Resources by Faculty and Students

From the above tables, it has been evinced that both the faculty and student respondents need 'more discipline-oriented e-journals and e-books' to be added and it was also evinced that 'practical hands on training' by faculty respondents and 'personal assistance on special features' by student respondents are considered as the most required suggestions for improving the 'usage of N-LIST e-resources'.

Findings

- It has been assessed that the students, i.e., 61.27% considered 'lack of awareness regarding database literacy' as a major hindrance/problem faced by them while using N-LIST e-resources whereas the faculty, i.e., 52.09% feel that their 'research problems' remained unsolved.
- Both the faculty and student respondents encountered in 'lack of technical know-how' as the second major hindrance while using the N-LIST e-resources.
- Both of the faculty and students respondents find difficulty in framing the search strategy. Thus, it is evident that the users need formal training programs conducted by the libraries.
- A majority of faculty respondents i.e. 77.08% feels that 'more discipline-oriented e-books should be added', which is considered as the most relevant suggestion followed by 75.70% of faculty respondents considered 'practical hands on training' as an extremely relevant suggestion for improving access to N-LIST e-resources.
- It is inferred that the 'addition of more discipline-oriented e-books' and 'practical hands on training' are considered as the most relevant and apt suggestion by the faculty respondents for improving the 'usage of N-LIST e-resources'.
- A majority of student respondents 92.25% and 90.84% preferred more discipline-oriented e-journals and e-books to be added for better browsing followed by 90.85% participants who considered their urge for training on special features as a relevant suggestion for improving the Usage of N-LIST e-resources.

Suggestions and Recommendations

The study at hand focused on the evaluation of usage of N-LIST e-resources in the select degree colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. The libraries should endeavor to launch a marketing plan to promote the usage of N-LIST e-resources and its awareness among the users

through email alerts, text messages, social networking sites, whatsapp groups, blogs, wikis, etc. It is suggested that the subscription cost of N-LIST e-resources should be reduced to the same as earlier for the non-aided colleges also.

Further research in this regard will widen the criteria of the study and identify as to how the faculty and the student from the member colleges affiliated to other universities explore the usage of the N-LIST e-resources. The authors feel that there is a need for appropriate and constant evaluation of this study in order to enhance insight into the usage analysis and the relevance of the information retrieved from the N-LIST e-resources.

References

1. Akinola SF. Information seeking behaviour of lecturers in faculties of education in Obafemi Awolowo University, Heilife and University of Ibadan. *Samaru Journal of Information Studies* 2009; 9(2): 30.
2. Bhardwaj RK, Walia PK. Web based information sources and services: A case study of St. Stephen's College, University of Delhi. *Library Philosophy and Practice* <http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/bhardwaj-walia.html>. 2012.
3. Chattwal A. Information seeking behaviour of social science faculty: a study of universities of Punjab, Haryana and Chandigarh. (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis). Panjab University, Chandigarh (India). 2014.
4. Kumbar D, Chikkamanju, Kumar GK. Use of N-LIST e-resources by the faculty and student of University of Mysore Constituent Degree Colleges: A comparative study. *National Seminar on Emerging Trends in ERMS in College Libraries 2013*: 6. ISBN: 978-93-83302-01-7.
5. Krejcie RV, Morgan DW. Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurements* 1970; 30, 607-10.
6. Nikam K, Pramodini B. Use of e-journals and databases by the academic community of University of Mysore: A survey. *Annals of Library and Information Studies* 2007; 54(1): 19-22.
7. Proportionate Random Stratified Sampling. In *Stattrek.com*. 2013. Retrieved on May 18, 2013. <http://stattrek.com/statistics/resources.aspx>
8. Sethi B, Panda KC. Use of e-resources by life scientists: a case study of Sambalpur University, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice* 2012: Paper 681. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/681>
9. Chikkanmanju, Kumbar M. Use of information resources and services by the students of first grade colleges affiliated to Tumkur University, Tumkur: A comparative study. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science* 2015; 3(2), 53-64.

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